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Є. І. НАСЕДКІН, канд. геол. наук, ст. дослідник, ст. наук. співроб. (Інститут геологічних наук НАН України), експерт з геології (Національний екологічний центр України), nasedevg@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2633-9291>,

Р. Б. ГАВРИЛЮК, канд. геол. наук, ст. дослідник, заст. директора (Інститут геологічних наук НАН України), голова (Національний екологічний центр України), gavrilyuk.ruslan@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6465-9440>,

В. М. БАЛІНСЬКИЙ, співроб. (Національний екологічний центр України), v.balinsky@gw.necu.org.ua, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-5036-7897>,

Л. В. ФЕДОРЕНКО, канд. біол. наук, ст. наук. співроб. (Інститут гідробіології НАН України), fedorenko20071979@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7241-0282>

Ye. NASIEDKIN, Candidate of Geological Sciences, Senior Researcher (Institute of Geological Sciences of NAS of Ukraine), Expert in Geology (National Ecological Center of Ukraine), nasedevg@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2633-9291>,

R. HAVRYLIUK, Candidate of Geological Sciences, Deputy Director (Institute of Geological Sciences of NAS of Ukraine), Head (National Ecological Center of Ukraine), gavrilyuk.ruslan@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6465-9440>,

V. BALINSKY, employee (National Ecological Centre of Ukraine), v.balinsky@gw.necu.org.ua, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-5036-7897>,

L. FEDORENKO, Candidate of Biological Sciences, Senior Researcher (Institute of Hydrobiology of NAS of Ukraine), fedorenko20071979@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7241-0282>

ГЕОЕКОЛОГІЧНІ АСПЕКТИ ОЦІНКИ НАСЛІДКІВ ЗНИЩЕННЯ КАХОВСЬКОГО ВОДОСХОВИЩА

GEOECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ASSESSING THE CONSEQUENCES OF KAKHOVKA RESERVOIR DESTRUCTION

Розглянуто один з найменш вивчених аспектів проблеми визначення шкоди, завданої руйнацією греблі Каховської ГЕС, пов'язаний з винесенням водного масиву водосховища нижче за течією Дніпра. Крім соціальних та економічних втрат, ця подія мала значні негативні екологічні наслідки для екосистем величезних територій як вище, так і нижче підірваної греблі, насамперед пов'язані зі зміною гідрологічних і гідрогеологічних умов. Досліджено таку важливу складову екологічної оцінки, як урахування шкоди від перенесення низки поллютантів, накопичених у донних відкладах Каховського водосховища в пониззя Дніпра, Дніпро-Бузький лиман і північно-західну частину Чорного моря. Проведено аналіз літературних джерел та окреслено основні завдання та складові геохімічної оцінки стану донних відкладів акваторії до катастрофи, визначено інструменти їх реалізації. Акцентовано увагу на необхідності врахування фактичного розподілу різних типів донних відкладів, сформованих в акваторії до знищення греблі, їхніх якісних і кількісних характеристик, сорбційних властивостей та регіональних закономірностей вмісту в них різних типів забруднювачів. Обґрунтовано доцільність застосування моделювання переміщення саме поверхневих шарів донних відкладів з урахуванням їх фізичних властивостей, гідрофізичних і гідрохімічних умов формування стоку Дніпра протягом перших тижнів після катастрофи як для акваторії Каховського водосховища (процеси реседиментації та винесення), так і нижче розташованих акваторій (процеси седиментації та накопичення). В практичній площині такі дослідження сприятимуть створенню фактологічної бази для визначення впливу Каховської катастрофи на донні біоценози, рекреаційні та природоохоронні території як лівобережних, так і правобережних територій пониззя Дніпра, а також формуванню відповідних прогнозних показників у різних часових і просторових діапазонах.

Ключові слова: Каховська катастрофа, седиментація, донні відклади, пониззя Дніпра, забруднювачі, оцінка шкоди.

The article reveals one of the least studied aspects of the problem of determining the damage caused by the destruction of the Kakhovka hydroelectric power plant dam, namely, the removal of the reservoir's water mass downstream of the Dnipro River. In addition to the social and economic losses, this event had significant negative environmental consequences for vast areas both above and below the undermined dam, primarily related to changes in hydrological and hydrogeological conditions. In the article an important component of environmental assessment as definition of harm from the transfer of a number of pollutants that had accumulated in the bottom sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir in the lower reaches of the Dnipro River, the Dnipro-Bug estuary and the northwestern part of the Black Sea is considered. The main tasks and components of the geochemical assessment of bottom sediments before the destruction of the dam, and the tools for their implementation are outlined. In particular, we focused on the necessity to take into account the distribution of various types of bottom sediments formed in the water area before dam destruction, their qualitative and quantitative characteristics, and the content of various types of pollutants in them. The rationale for employing sediment transport modeling, considering the physical properties of the sediments, as well as the hydro-physical and hydrochemical conditions of the Dnipro's runoff formation in the initial weeks after the disaster, is substantiated for both the Kakhovka Reservoir area (resedimentation and removal processes) and the downstream aquatic zones (sedimentation processes). In practical terms, such studies will contribute to the creation of a factual basis for determining the impact of the Kakhovka disaster on benthic biocenoses, recreational and protected areas, as well as the development of relevant predictive indicators.

Keywords: Kakhovka disaster, sedimentation, bottom sediments, lower Dnipro River, pollutants, damage assessment.

Introduction

As a result of the terrorist act by the Russian occupiers on June 6, 2023, the dam of the Kakhovka hydroelectric power plant was destroyed and the largest reservoir in Ukraine by area was destroyed. This water storage facility played an important role in the southern regions of Ukraine. The negative consequence of the dam destruction, among other things, was the relocation of a number of pollutants (radionuclides, persistent organic pollu-

tants, heavy metals, oil products, etc.) accumulated in the bottom sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir in the lower reaches of the Dnipro, Dnipro-Bug estuary and the northwestern part of the Black Sea. A significant component in determining the damage caused to these water areas, and in the future, its minimization, should be a high-quality geochemical assessment of bottom sediments state before these events, study of the volumes of pollutant removal in suspension and in a soluble state during the disaster

and modeling their further distribution downstream, taking into account hydrophysical and hydrochemical processes.

Analysis of preliminary research and problem formulation

After the Kakhovka dam disaster, a significant number of studies were carried out by Ukrainian scientists, governmental and non-governmental organizations to determine and assess the potential damage caused by the removal of suspended matter from the reservoir through washout in dam blown up by Russian troops. The published materials included a rough estimate of re-sedimented bottom sediments transport using satellite data, as well as contact studies of the drained reservoir bed above the dam and in places of temporary flooding downstream along the Dnipro River [2, 6, 13, 17, 19, 20].

But these research materials paid almost no attention to qualitative assessment of the surface layer of bottom sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir, which had accumulated for almost 70 years. After the dam was blown up their most dispersed component was transferred by the water flow to a suspended state and moved from the reservoir water area together with the water mass and subsequently settled in the lower reaches of Dnipro River, the water areas of Dnipro-Bug Estuary and northwestern part of the Black Sea.

Considering the silts dominance in the sedimentary material, as well as the fact that approximately 99.5% of the material entering the Kakhovka Reservoir sedimented in its basin [12] (according to recalculations in absolute values, this amounted to 52.9×10^6 out of 53.17×10^6 tons/year), it can be confidently stated that a huge amount of suspended material, which formed over a long period of time under conditions of stable technogenic pressure, was simultaneously displaced.

It should be noted that the study of the distribution, qualitative and quantitative characteristics of surface bottom sediments formed in the water area of an artificial reservoir during its existence is an important key for determining both the damage caused to the lower reaches of the Dnipro River and the Black Sea after the dam break, and the prospects for further use of the drained territory.

Material and discussion

It is well known that surface bottom sediments are the main “sedimentation tanks” and concentrators of most pollutants in water areas, especially in artificial reservoirs created to accumulate water masses for use in industry and agriculture. Due to a number of physical, chemical, hydrological and hydrobiological processes, pollutants accumulate in suspended matter and enter the surface layer (less stable, loose and waterlogged) of bottom sediments in areas of least hydrodynamic activity. This is typical of large shallow reservoirs with slow movement of water flows within the lower part of the water area, where the processes of suspension transfer caused by wave activity and currents lead to its separation and fractional accumulation on the bottom surface.

The maximum amount of metals such as Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr, Cd within the Dnipro River cascade reservoirs is characteristic of the southern reservoirs which are located in industrial zones (the Dnipro and Kakhovka reservoirs). The highest concentrations were found in clayey silts [16] (for dry matter: Fe 11,600–32,400; Mn 1,504–3,450; Cu 38.9–85.5; Zn 89.8–186.5; Cr 48.6–193.0; Cd 1.9–4.4 mg/kg⁻¹). For this type of bottom sediments, which were studied within the central parts of the reservoir, the main sources of heavy metals were considered to be both technogenic factors (the impact of mining and metallurgical production and chemical plants) and natural conditions (low current velocities, that allow toxic components to be carried away and accumulate in the most dispersed component of bottom sediments) [8].

In the geochemical aspect, that was due to the connection of most heavy metals with oxides and hydroxides of iron and manganese (Mn 74–93%; Zn 43–70%; Fe 27–59%; Cd 28–41%), as well as the presence of organic matter, the concentration of which in silt sediments reached 12% [1].

In 2015–2022 we carried out field research at a geoecological testing ground [3, 9] within Zaporizhzhia city (on the Dnipro River section downstream from the Dnipro hydroelectric power plant, actually located several kilometers from the upper reaches of the Kakhovka Reservoir) [2]. The results of our investigations showed similar trends. Flows of finely dispersed suspended matter were the main carriers of iron and manganese oxides, as well as heavy metals associated with them. That matter forms the upper layer of sediments in certain areas in accordance with the underwater relief with minimal hydrodynamic activity and are represented by a finely dispersed pelitic substance enriched with a metal-containing component, consisting of mixed-layer formations of chlorite-illite-montmorillonite and skeletal remains of siliceous microalgae. In the bottom areas with hydrodynamic disturbances psamitic component of sediments on their surface dominates. It contains a minimum of pollutants and consists of quartz sands of different sizes with a minimum presence of a finely dispersed iron-containing component (Fig. 1).

The chemical composition of samples indicates that the substance represented by the finely dispersed component significantly enriched with a number of metals and a decrease of these metals content in sand-sized sediments. Such features of various lithological and material-genetic types of marine sediments to accumulate a number of microelements from the aquatic environment are well known [10].

The same trend is observed in the patterns of radioactive contamination of different types of bottom sediments, in particular in Kyiv Reservoir. Studies of the contaminated areas of its bottom were conducted in 1989–1991 and duplicated almost twenty

Fig. 1. SEM images and chemical composition of two types of sediments collected in areas with different hydrodynamics and bottom geomorphology within the geoecological testing ground (within Zaporizhzhia city) [3]: a) finely dispersed silt-clay matter enriched with iron, consisting of mixed-layered formations of chlorite-illite-montmorillonite; b) rounded fragments of quartz grains and fragments of feldspars of sand size, with an insignificant admixture of aggregated clay component

years later (2008–2010) [6]. They showed that the main amount of radionuclides accumulated after the first years of the Chernobyl disaster accident at the places where flowing of watercourses into this artificial reservoir shifted to the deep-water areas of the middle and lower parts of the reservoir. It was indicated that the shallow areas became cleaner, and in the deep-water areas the total amount of ^{137}Cs increased due to the natural gradual growth of silt layer. So, as in case of heavy metals distribution, a gradual concentration of the layer with the maximum contamination occurred in zones of stable accumulation of the fine clay component and not directly related to the locations of pollution income.

The Kakhovka Reservoir was the largest water-intake facility of the Cascade of Dnipro River reservoirs (the total volume of water-intake from the reservoir could exceed $900 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). [15]. It served as a source of drinking water supply for the cities of Nikopol, Marhanets, Pokrov and a number of populated areas; water was taken into the North Crimean, Kakhovka and Dnipro-Kryvyi Rih canals, the North Rogachytska, Verkhno-Tarasivska and Nikopol irrigation systems, and supplied water to the Zaporizhzhia State District Power Plant. These factors affected the characteristics of water exchange (the lowest flow rate in the cascade, did not exceeding 1.8 cm/s). The Kakhovka Reservoir became the largest concentrator of fine clay component in the bottom sediments. 82% of the water area bottom was silted up; the average vertical thickness of bottom sediments was 0.19 m , reaching 1 m in some areas. Silt predominated over sand among the main granulometric fractions of the sediments that accumulated during the existence of the Kakhovka Reservoir before the disaster [12].

The slow water exchange in the reservoir's water area with a relatively stable content of heavy metals in the aquatic environment of both the surface and bottom layers [15] formed processes of secondary water pollution, mainly of a seasonal nature [8]. It took place in summer and autumn, when water consumption increased, and as the result the concentrations of heavy metals were 2–5 times higher than in the spring. Such natural balance between the distribution of the amount of elements in solution and suspended form depends on a number of external factors: changes in the acidity of the environment; size, composition and distribution density of suspended matter in the aquatic environment; and the hydrodynamic and hydrochemical regime of the water area. According to [7], a clear relationship between the soluble and suspended phases is not evident for all heavy metals; an increase of river water turbidity is accompanied by a decrease of Pb, Cd, Mn concentration in filtered water, while the concentrations of Cu and Zn remain stable. This indicates the need to take into account the possibility of their transition between the aqueous phase and the suspended component when studying the removal and distribution of pollutants in the composition of bottom sediments.

Silty mud was noticeably dominant in the upper and middle parts of the reservoir, clayer mud dominated in the lower part and sands were located in small zones in the upper part. In the lower part of the reservoir, an increase in all the main finely dispersed fractions was observed, which was explained by the processes of their transportation down the reservoir and sedimentation in deeper areas (Fig. 2). The zone of continuous accumulation of the fine clay component in the deep part of the reservoir began below Novooleksandrivka and extended to the Kakhovka dam, the thickness of the mud layer was 10–20 cm (in the section from Vasylivka and below, the thickness of the layer was even higher) [12].

Fig. 2. Distribution maps of: a) main granulometric types of bottom sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir; b) accumulation capacities of subaqueous sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir [12]. Islands are not indicated on the diagrams

The decoding data of the satellite imagery of the drained reservoir bed [6] and their comparison with the maps of the distribution of bottom sediments before the destruction of the dam showed the absence of the specified mass of the fine clay component of sediments in the Novooleksandrivka village – Kakhovka Hydroelectric Power Plant section. The intensity of the water flow in this narrow part of the reservoir in the first days of the disaster caused the transition of the finely dispersed component of bottom sediments accumulated over a decade into a suspended state and its transportation downstream. Fine clay mud (the maximum natural concentrator of pollution in bottom sediments) in huge volumes were carried by the water flow from the exploded dam and settled in accordance with natural conditions in the area of Dnipro River – Dnipro – Bug estuary – Black Sea waters, within hydrodynamically passive zones, geochemical barriers and other areas with favorable sedimentation processes.

Determining the volume of mud accumulated during the existence of the reservoir and the content of hazardous, including man-made components in it opens up the possibility of assessing the damage caused to the environment of the lower reaches of Dnipro River, estuaries and shelf of the Black Sea by specific types of pollutants. This can be done by modeling the removal of pollutants taking into account the hydrophysical and hydrochemical conditions of the Dnipro runoff during the first weeks after the disaster. Input information for such calculations should

include a high-quality retrospective analysis of: distribution of various types of bottom sediments in the water area of the Kakhovka Reservoir before the dam was blown up; formation conditions; physical and chemical properties and concentrations of the main pollutants in their composition. Quantitative indicators of the distribution of volumes of different types of sediments within a water area can be determined using the absolute mass method, which is one of the most important tools for the actual study of the sedimentation process in continental and marine basins [12].

Conclusion

Determining the volume of sediments accumulated during the existence of the reservoir and the content of technogenic components in them opens up opportunities for further assessment of the damage caused to the lower reaches of Dnipro River, estuaries and the Black Sea shelf by specific types of pollutants, as well as prospects for further use of the drained territory of the reservoir. This becomes possible if we do the following:

1. Geocological assessment of the layer of bottom sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir, which accumulated over the course of its almost 70-year existence:

- distribution of different types of bottom sediments formed in the water area;
- qualitative (dimension, composition) indicators of bottom sediments;
- quantitative characteristics of bottom sediments (approximate volume estimate);
- content of different types of pollutants in sediments (radionuclides, persistent organic pollutants, heavy metals, petroleum products, etc.).

2. Modeling the movement of bottom sediments taking into account their physical properties, hydrophysical and hydrochemical conditions of the formation of Dnipro runoff during the first weeks after the disaster both for the water area of Kakhovka Reservoir (processes of resedimentation and removal) and for the downstream water areas (processes of sedimentation and accumulation).

Such work will help to recognize the changes that occurred in the drained areas of the reservoir bed as part of the development of various types of bottom sediments during the period of subaqueous formation conditions, and will help to determine the prospects for their further economic use. Also, based on modeling, it is possible to preliminarily determine the changes in the distribution features of the material-genetic types of bottom sediments in the lower reaches of the Dnipro River (including the estuaries and the northwestern Shelf of the Black Sea), which occurred in the first months after the disaster, and also to predict the nature and direction of modern sedimentation processes. In practical terms, these studies will contribute to the creation of a factual basis for identifying the impact of the Kakhovka disaster on bottom biocenoses, recreational and nature conservation areas, as well as the formation of corresponding forecast indicators.

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автори – Майя Лаврінок, Михайло Камаса

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Для посадових осіб надрокористувачів, науковців, викладачів і студентів ЗВО в галузях геології, права, менеджменту, екології та управління, посадових осіб правоохоронних органів, громадських організацій у сфері екології та геології, адвокатів, які спеціалізуються на надрокористуванні, посадових осіб органів влади (Держгеонадр, Держекоінспекції, Міндовкілля, Мінекономіки, Держпраці, Держводагенства, Кабінету Міністрів України, Ради національної безпеки і оборони України) та місцевого самоврядування, працівників суду та прокуратури.

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